

IMMERSIVE AND INTERACTIVE MUSIC FOR EVERYONE

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to understand how new and accessible technology can be used and developed to include producers of standard music into making immersive, interactive, music experiences. Through observations during a student project and an analysis of the participant's reflections it argues that even if the technology worked well, there are still many opportunities for improvements. The result shows that the repeated, non-creative, tasks like exporting and naming files can reduce musical inspiration for students with little interest in technology and that further development and studies potentially could make interactive music accessible even for them. The aspect of the project that caused most positive response was producing and mixing for super-surround which led the students to new insights and ideas for their everyday music production. Finally the result indicates that even if there would have been no technical barriers interactive music production might not appeal to everyone. Interactive music should maybe be seen as a separate discipline and students with a linear approach to composition will not necessarily find it interesting.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development and design of digital technology over the last decades have brought us new tools for creativity that are both cheaper and easier to use than previous products. Applications that previously were expensive and technically advanced are now available free or for a low cost for people with little or no prior experience. In the music production field where expensive, analog equipment used to be the only option, Digital Audio Workstations (DAW) [1] now have made music production inexpensive and accessible for everyone with a computer [2]. Interactive and immersive environments like spatialization of musical sound [3] are increasingly important research fields. Music production for these environments is a more complex task [4] and is not yet accessible for most music producers. This study adds to earlier work on composition and arrangement techniques for interactive music [5] seeking to get a better understanding of current challenges and potential solutions for the making of immersive, interactive

music. It hopefully contributes to making these music formats accessible for music producers with little or no prior programming skills.

1.1 Earlier experiences

The Royal College of Music (KMH)¹ was founded 1771 and has a wide range of educations for musicians, composers and music teachers in different genres. Since 2001 there is also a bachelor's program in music production. Most of those students have a background in pop and rock music but through different courses they get to try music production for different targets. This could typically involve producing music for film, computer games, web pages and interactive installations. The students are normally mixing for stereo but during the education they also learn how to mix music for other formats like 5.1 and multi-channel. Every year since 2013, different student groups have produced multi-channel, interactive music installations for different venues including Kulturhuset,² Stockholm City Museum,³ Nobel Creations [6] at Nobel Prize Museum⁴ and The Sound Forest [7] at the Museum of Performing Arts⁵.

Figure 1. Student interacting with her music production in Klangkupolen.

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¹ <http://www.kmh.se>

² <http://kulturhusetstadsteatern.se>

³ <http://stadsmuseet.stockholm.se>

⁴ <http://nobelprizemuseum.se>

⁵ <http://scenkonstmuseet.se>

1.2 The project

This study was conducted alongside a course-based project at KMH 2019. The students were introduced to general concepts and the technical framework through seminars, tutorials and workshops to prepare for the project. The course description defined the project to be a music production for “Klangkupolen” [8] - a multi-channel, super-surround speaker setup - where the music playback should be controlled by the audience using two or more smartphones (see fig.1). The technical framework was built upon the source code from earlier works and adjusted for this particular case.

2. TECHNICAL SYSTEM

The technical system is built around iMusic⁶ - a javascript framework for organizing and playing back audio in interactive environments. Beside iMusic, smaller components have been developed to add features like socket communication, webcam control and synchronization. iMusic is the result of an artistic participatory design process [9] at KMH, involving students and teachers in interactive music projects.

The development of the technology (except Klangkupolen itself) follows three design goals: No cost, no installation requirements and easy-to-use. These goals lead to the use of smartphones as sensors (while all participants already have one), an available Mac-Book as the main computer (but could have been any standard computer) and open source, javascript libraries (as they are free and the only language the students know). The following sections describe the three software components (client, server and master) forming the technical framework for this project (see fig.2). All source-code is available for download⁷.

Figure 2. Technical system for the project.

2.1 Client

The client application was developed as a mobile web page and uses the browser’s built-in Device Orientation API⁸ to record the mobile’s movement around the y and z axis. The client’s only task is to capture the participants’ hand movements and pass the information on to a server. The communication between the client and server runs on a standard WiFi-connection and uses a framework called socket.io⁹.

⁶ <http://github.com/hanslindetorp/imusic>

⁷ <http://hans.arapoviclindetorp.se/klangkupolen2019>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/orientation-event/>

⁹ <https://socket.io>

To optimize performance without overloading networks and processors, a refresh rate of 100Hz was chosen. In addition to this streaming data, the library shake.js¹⁰ was used to notify the server when the mobiles were shaken. The client was successfully tested on both iOS / Safari and Android / Chrome in current versions and also on older mobiles such as iPhone 5 with iOS 10. The biggest challenge was to prevent the phone from automatically activate sleep-mode when not touched for a while and made it clear that smartphones primarily are built for touch interactions and visual feedback.

2.2 Server

The server’s function is to receive data from the clients and send it to the master application. Inspired by solutions like Soundworks [10] from the CoSiMa project, the server is a web server developed on the node.js¹¹ platform with express.js and socket.io to manage the communication between the various devices. The application was developed generically to be easily reused in future projects with one single function for clients to pass on data to each other or, as in this case, to a master. Even if node.js is free to download, it requires an installation. The server does therefore not fully meet the design goals.

2.3 Master

The master application controls the audio and is built with three main layers dealing with audio playback, music mapping and communication. The audio playback is controlled by the iMusic framework which is built upon a standard web API called Web Audio API and handles loading and buffering of audio data, synchronization of audio files, looping, randomization and real-time modulation of sounds using parameters like volume, panning, filter, delay, reverb and more. iMusic runs in all browsers supporting Web Audio API, but it varies to what degree they conform to the specification. In this case Google Chrome was chosen as it supports 32 separate output channels. During this project the following features were added to iMusic:

- Mapping a control value to an audio parameter which made it possible for a student with little programming experience to map any sensor data to any audio parameter in the system.
- Multi-channel panning which let the students specify a list of audio channels between which the sensor data could control the position of a sound.
- Addressing any internal audio bus to any number of output channels which made it possible to send reverb for a particular sound to a specified set of speakers.
- Envelope curves controlling audio parameters which was used in this project to connect an event from a client to trigger a volume change on a reverb bus.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/alexgibson/shake.js>

¹¹ <https://nodejs.org/en/>

The music mapping is separated into a script written by the students. In this script they define the musical structure including organizing the files into iMusic's predefined musical objects; looped tracks, parts, motifs and variations through a file name convention system. (see fig.3)

Figure 3. Example of the file naming convention

Another feature of the music mapping is to determine how the incoming sensor data should control the music. In interactive music production, this is crucial to the final result and sometime as important as the composition and recording. Most students wanted to connect one or several incoming data streams to control an audio parameter. This could typically be to connect the tilting of a smartphone to control the volume of a sound. They also connected shake events to trigger the playback of a certain sound.

3. METHOD

This study was conducted alongside a student project 2019 at KMH. Twelve students - seven female and five male students between the ages of 21-36 - took part in the project and contributed to the study with feedback during the supervised sessions and through written reflections after the project. The reflections should answer the following questions and the students gave their permission for their texts to be analysed and quoted anonymously for research purposes. After the texts were analyzed, quotes were collected and sorted to find common themes.

- What was your responsibility and what skills did you develop through the project?
- Which parts of the course have been important for the project and how have you gained from them?
- What parts of the result are you extra happy with and what would you recommend students in coming projects to do in a similar way?
- What would you recommend students in coming projects to do in a different way?

4. RESULT

The text analyses pointed out three themes; “non-linear music”, “interactivity” and “multi-channel”. The following sections presents these three themes plus a few separate thoughts and ideas formulated by the students.

4.1 Non-linear music

Many students described that the biggest challenge in this project was to produce non-linear music (music without a predetermined form). Like the participants in previous studies [11], they recognized that it was a bit like “telling a story to someone without ever coming to the end”. Especially students with a singer / songwriter background who usually create music based on their voice and an instrument described that this step required “a completely different way of thinking” or that they “did not know how to think”. They felt that their music became static, that they were struggling with being too much in control and that it was difficult not to get stuck in a particular thinking. One student also stated that “with interactive music, an important parameter in the narrative technique disappears, namely the time the audience is exposed to a certain part of the piece.”

The students who usually produce loop-based music more easily related to the non-linear form and expressed that “Every song you write is at some stage non-linear until you record it” and “I’m used to working with loops and like to have DAW projects with several small beats I cut and move (also live) which made me feel comfortable”. One student experienced this part of the project as the most stimulating and wrote “The most fun I thought was to play with rhythms, to insert short rhythmic loops that played randomly and in different constellations with other random rhythm loops”.

When the students were asked how to take on the task if they were to do a similar project again, they emphasized starting with a musical idea that reflects a feeling rather than one from the technology, to release the need for control and to choose softer sounds and to use sounds that are difficult to get tired of.

4.2 Interactivity

More than half of the students described that a large part of the production time was used to deal with the technical challenges relating to interactivity. They formulated e.g. “Having to name the audio files in a certain way and cutting them up in different parts for it to work, killed my creative process along the way.” And “In the interactive world with our technical knowledge, this step takes an incredible amount of energy and the result can be like that.” Several students described how they had to lower their musical ambitions because the technical work took so much time. When they got over the technical barriers, they also experienced challenges related to interactivity and music and described e.g. “Creating something user-friendly requires a lot of testing and exploration.” And that “in order for the interaction to work in a practical way, you have to use extremes to make the listener perceive the difference.” The challenge of getting a final, musical result that they like when listeners are controlling the playback was also highlighted as well as the difficulty of using vocal tracks in an enjoyable way without a nagging and annoying result.

The students who expressed themselves more positively about their results were particularly satisfied with the interactions that were easy for the participants to understand

and sounds that invited them to play and interact with. According to the students, complex solutions were not always preferable to simple ones and one student described that “A simple sinewave with pitch-bend controlled by tilting the phone became a successful instrument. It was incredibly responsive and fun to play with and also contributed to the composition”.

The students contributed with recommendations for producing music for interactivity and mentioned “to start from a musical idea rather than a technical”, “decide what would be controlled by the producer and what would be influenced by the participants”, “make sure that all parts are fun to play with”, “make the background layer minimalistic so it doesn’t collide with the participants interactions” and “use short samples with fast attack for the interactions”.

4.3 Multi-channel

Many of the students was euphoric about the possibility of producing music for Klangkupolen and used adjectives like “crazy”, “funny”, “special” and that they were “completely sold on the idea”. One student described the experience in the following words:

“Being in such an open area and surrounded by music was really wonderful. I couldn’t help but dance to the faster, more rhythmic songs while the quieter, more meditative compositions got me and some classmates to lay down on the ground to take in the music.”

This quote both confirms the spatial concept with super-surround and reveals that when the listener is laying down on the floor, the immersive perspective is removed and Klangkupolen is turned into a multi-channel system in front of the listener. The challenges the students highlighted were that it is a huge difference to mix for a 29.4 system compared to stereo and that they needed more time to test their music and adjust their mixes to achieve better results. One student stated that when mixing in stereo one never thinks about how it should sound behind the listener because there is no “behind” in a stereo mix. On the other hand, there is no specified “front” in the Klangkupolen and the listener can experience the music faced in any direction.

Further thoughts that were highlighted were that Klangkupolen invites you to “compose the piece for the room rather than writing from a musical flow”, that Klangkupolen can add a new dimension to the meaning of a song and that the sounds “thrown between different sides of the room” can be linked to the meaning of the lyrics. One student thought it was, in one way, easier to create a meaningful musical experience for Klangkupolen than for stereo because panning and levels become more important than details in the music. Several students also expressed how Klangkupolens visual factor invites both to create powerful and “big” music and that those who come to listen to music there will experience something cool just by seeing the room.

4.4 Other thoughts and ideas

Some students further reflected on new experiences and that will benefit their regular music production. One insight was to use a more minimalistic approach without adding instruments that will not be heard in the final mix. One student reasoned that the technical knowledge required in interaction design and programming prevent many music producers from exploring music production for interactive environments. Another student was excited to have produced something that became a creative place where people could meet and create something new together. Finally, some got ideas for new applications and suggested a music format for i.e. Spotify where a part of a song could be interactive and someone else could see an interactive music installation in Klangkupolen which was like a game. Finally, a quote that captures both the opportunities and challenges of creating interactive music and also problematizes the boundary between the composer and the participants:

“It should not only sound good but also be fun to participate in. If you give too little control to the audience, it loses its point of being interactive. If you, on the other hand, give them too much control, it may lose the point of composing it at all in advance.”

5. DISCUSSION

This project included several new challenges for the students, each of which would be interesting to study separately. It was obvious that students were euphoric about the immersive sound in Klangkupolen and that the project gave them important ideas for their traditional productions. Therefore, probably a super-surround project would be valuable in itself, without the interactive elements. More than half of the group expressed their frustration with making music for interactions in a non-linear structure, mostly expressed by students with a typical singer / songwriter background. The students with a more loop-based approach in their normal music production was in contrast more positive and engaged more in learning the possibilities with the technical framework. This observation points towards viewing interactive music production as a different discipline compared to standard music production. Maybe technology will never solve the gap between a songwriter and a non-linear context simply because the songwriter wants to express a linear story.

The other group, the students who managed to pass the technical and practical barriers, expressed that this project had given them new perspectives on how their music can work when it becomes a platform for interaction and communication between people. This was said by students with no earlier experience of producing music for interactions and it motivates more attempts to make the technology even more easy to use for those who have no prior experience in programming and interactivity. A challenge to look further into in future studies is how this type of technology can be designed to be easier to use without limiting

the creative possibilities for the music producer. The evaluation of the technical platform also led to a few important observations:

- Open source, installation free, web-based technology performs well enough to work as a platform for projects like this.
- There is huge community developing for web technologies and there will probably be a continuous increase in libraries for sensor detection.
- The web API's are still quite new and not that well established. It's important to constantly read about the latest specification changes to make an application sustainable when the users browser auto-updates.
- The web is primarily made for visual interfaces with touch control and this becomes a problem when using it for a different purpose. In this project especially the auto-play blocking policy and the automatic sleep-mode was causing problems to the interactions.

6. CONCLUSION

Using mobile phones, web technology and Klangkupolen to make immersive music interaction accessible for students with no prior experience was in many ways successful and also gave insights into some challenges. Even if some of the technical barriers were removed, the workflow could be even easier and more fluent. The result also indicates that the artistic challenge to produce music for interactivity differs a lot from standard music production and might not appeal to all. The immersive experience offered by Klangkupolen gave the students valuable insights and an increased interest in trying new approaches in music production. KMH's unique technical infrastructure together with the ongoing development of everyday technology such as mobiles, smart watches and web technology can potentially make projects like this even more accessible to many generations of students in the future.

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